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Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to present the illustration of quality control approach, which has been adopted by several organizations, in order to manage and improve their production processes. The approach is referred as total quality management (TQM). This study will discuss the implementation of TQ, within the working environment of Nike Inc. One of the major objectives behind the implementation of TQ is to reduce or completely eliminate potential errors and flaws, within the manufacturing process, in order to improve quality of services and products, customer satisfaction, and ensuring environmental sustainability (Davrajh & Bright, 2013). The proceeding study will help in understanding the core concept of TQ, while designing a TQ initiative for Nike, Inc. The research will also present the evaluation of impact of the team mean, while assessing the strengths and weaknesses of the plan.

Discussion

Premise of TQ

It has been claimed by Goetsch and Davis (2014) that quality can be understood as the distinguishing attribute or a degree of excellence. In other words, quality can be considered as the degree to which a product or a service lives up to its maintainability, endurance, performance, and order characteristics that a consumer expects to get from the product. One of the major objectives of total quality management is to attain enduring success through customer satisfaction. According to Distelhorst, et al (2014), the approach of total quality management is based on the contribution of all members of an organization to improve and enhance the quality of services, products, and processes of the company. In accordance with the views of Davrajh and Bright (2013), TQM incorporates different effective management approaches, technical tools, and existing improvement efforts to foster continual improvement within the organizational operations.

TQ Initiative for Nike

Total quality has become one of the greatest priorities of the businesses and organizations. It is due to the fact that total quality helps the organizations to enhance and improve their operations while ensuring environmental integrity (Davrajh & Bright, 2013). Nike, Inc. is considered as one of the most leading and reputable companies, which is famous for producing and selling of footwear, accessories, equipments, apparel, and services (Goetsch & Davis, 2014). Therefore, the implementation of total quality initiative may considerably help the company in managing and ensuring the credibility of its operations. The proceeding section

incorporates the analysis of TQ initiative, which has been planned for Nike, in order to assure continuous improvement within the operations of Nike, Inc.

Plan

One of the initial and foremost steps, which are associated with the total quality initiatives, is referred as “plan”. In this step, the top tier management of the company examines and evaluates the current operations, in order to formulate organizational plans, accordingly. In this step, managers are responsible to identify problems, collect data, and document all current procedures and operations, which are being followed in the company (Distelhorst, et al, 2014). Therefore, in this step, all production and retailing operations of Nike will be examined and documented to bring more improvements in its daily routine processes.

Do

Second step of TQ initiative is to implement the formulated plan. During this step, managers are responsible for the documentation of changes, which have been occurred within the processes. One of the major objectives of this step is to examine the credibility and effectiveness of the changes (Davrajh & Bright, 2013). Thereby, in this step, the operational changes will be documented and recognized by the managers of Nike to ensure the integrity of company’s operations.

Study

Third step of TQ initiative is to study and examine the data, which is gathered during the second step. During this step, Nike's data will be evaluated, in order to ensure whether or not the developed plan is attaining the pre-defined goals (Goetsch & Davis, 2014).

Act

This step incorporates the communication practices, like meetings, in order to convey the results of the plan to the entire organization. In this step, the results of the formulated and implemented TQ plan will be communicated to the stakeholders of Nike, in order to bring more improvements through the suggestions of employees and other stakeholders (Distelhorst, et al, 2014).

Team Meeting to Disseminate the Plan in Nike

It is essential for the company, i.e., Nike to organize team meetings with the managers, in order to disseminate the plan. Team meetings may play an inevitable and incredible role in developing appropriate methods to disseminate the formulated plan to the entire company. In these meeting, different ways and methods will be discussed, which may help in communicating the plan to the employees of the company. In order to perform this activity, i.e., disseminating the formulated plan, different seminars and conferences will be organized (Goetsch & Davis, 2014). In addition to this, different training sessions will also be conducted to communicate this plan within the entire working environment of Nike. Moreover, reading materials, like manuals, will also be provided to the employees of Nike, to enhance their knowledge about the formulated plan, i.e., TQ plan (Oakland, 2014).

Impact of Meeting and Launching of TQ Plan in Nike

Team meetings may play a major role in communicating the objectives and expected outcomes of the plan. In addition to this, the launching of TQ plan may also assist Nike in improving and enhancing the integrity and credibility of their production and retailing operations (Davrajh & Bright, 2013). One of the greatest strengths of TQ plan, within the working environment of Nike, is to attain lowest manufacturing cost. Secondly, launching and implementation of TQ plan may also assist the company in ensuring sustainable production; hence, result in environmental integrity (Distelhorst, et al, 2014). On the other hand, launching of TQ plan may also pose different risks and threats to Nike.

Production disruption and employee resistance can be considered as one of the biggest threats, which are associated with the launching of TQ plan, within the working environment of Nike (Oakland, 2014). It is significant to notice that these threats can also be regarded as the weaknesses of launching TQ plan. These weaknesses can be easily managed by conducting different workshops and meetings, in order to motivate the employees.

Conclusion

From above discussion, it can be concluded that total quality has gained tremendous popularity in the past few decades. It is due to the fact that companies are intending to ensure long-term and continual benefits through achieving customer satisfaction, which can be attained by producing high quality products and services. In this regard, the preceding study has discussed the implementation of TQ initiative plan, to assure the reliability of Nike's working operations. The research has briefly elaborated the TQ plan, while discussing different ways of

disseminating the plan. Impacts of launching of TQ plan have also been analyzed in the study, while demonstrating two strengths and two weaknesses of the plan.

References

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